

Alternative ways of European participatory organic
fruit breeding projects

Research organisation for organic production

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Groupe de Recherche en Agriculture Biologique - Grab

Created in 1979, Grab is a non-profit organisation led by farmers and dedicated to research in organic farming.

The main objectives of the organisation are the following:

- **Improving organic techniques and systems**, especially in vegetables, fruits and grapevine growing.
- **Disseminating the knowledge** produced and innovations to all farmers.

Grab is the main French research organisation for organic production. The team of 16 people works on various topics such as cultivar assessment, functional biodiversity, agroforestry, plant protection, soil fertility... Most of the research is achieved on farmers plots.

Inn0Breed

Fruit cultivars with low susceptibility to pests and diseases

One of Grab's priorities deals with the research of fruit cultivars with low susceptibility to pests and diseases and adapted to their Mediterranean territory.

Mediterranean cultivars, either native to the region or grown there in the past, are often poorly known by farmers, newcomers or advisors, especially when it comes to their susceptibility to disease and pests. However, these cultivars have been adapted and may still be better adapted to climate and soil characteristics. Grab works on main southern fruit species such as apple, peach, apricot, almond...

This fruit heritage is maintained with no inputs (or in organic farming for some species), in the **Maison de la Biodiversité "la Thomassine"** of the **"Parc Naturel Régional du Luberon"**, in Manosque in France. Varieties are evaluated in this unique place (for further information, please follow the links below).

As these varieties are adapted to local conditions, and do not rely on plant protection, they can be recommended for organic farming or even be proposed as a genitor in a future plant breeding programme.

Partners of **Fruinov** and **DiversiGO** projects have made their best to describe this heritage and assess susceptibilities of cultivars for six to eight years from 2016 to 2023, depending on the species, and for three years in the case of pears.

These projects make all the data collected on these varieties (susceptibility, pomological data, etc.) available to the regional or national fruit chain, from grower to consumer. It proposes a participative assessment of these varieties through regular visits and the provision of an internet tool which brings together all the information collected and through which users can record their feedback, if they grow/know them.

For more information, please follow the links below:

[Parc du Luberon](#)

[La Thomassine](#)

[Fruinov](#)

InnOBreed collaboration

Since 2022, the Grab is part of the Horizon Europe project InnOBreed as a case study, joining a network of European colleagues working in the same field.

Thanks to Innobreed, Grab has been able to:

- **bring together methods and results on all varieties evaluated**
- **use innovative tools for faster cultivar assessment**
- **further valorise our results for new fruit breeding with a wider germplasm**
- **bring together the varieties identified as adapted for organic farming (low susceptibility to pests and diseases and adapted to local conditions)**
- **bring together the actors of organic fruit breeding, and initiate a work on a creation of new varieties for organic farmers**

Through Fruinov and DiversiGO projects, Grab has identified a few varieties with low susceptibility to pests and diseases. To achieve these results, an evaluation method was followed. All these results contribute to the objectives of InnOBreed and can be further used within the project.

Further information can be found here:

- [Parc du Luberon](#)
- [Article about the activities \(FR\)](#)
- [La Thomassine \(leaflet in FR\)](#)
- [La Thomassine \(video in FR\)](#)
- [GRAB: www.grab.fr](http://www.grab.fr)

Or contact Francois Warlop for further details: francois.warlop@grab.fr

